

Energy Consumption Forecast of University Buildings: Step towards Sustainable Educational Institutes: A Bibliometric Review

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ABSTRACT: Universities being knowledge hubs have to demonstrate sustainable practices in energy consumption. Energy forecast in university sector has got researchers attention as a step towards sustainable institutes. The application of a specific forecast study may vary; still it contributes directly or indirectly to the aim of having sustainable environment. Authors of this work conducted a bibliometric literature review to diagnose research tendency towards energy forecasting for universities. Novelty of this work lies in its focus on energy consumption forecast conducted in universities across the globe offering detailed insight. Diversity of the selected publications regarding different bibliometric angles has been demonstrated. An extensive outlook of the strategy used helps determine the research gaps in reviewed scientific articles. It has been found that the studies so far have been conducted by technical aspects with a minimal contribution from social sciences experts. Occupants and users significantly impact energy usage; however as input to energy forecast model this prospect has been considered by few authors, identifying a dimension for social experts to play role. Most contributing and prominent countries, universities, journals, publishers and authors in the field have been mentioned. Identification of research trend and gaps in current studies is the main academic contribution of this work.

Keywords: Energy, Forecasting, Universities, Sustainable campuses, Energy Prediction

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1. Introduction

Energy consumption and demand forecasting studies have received attention of the researchers the major driving force behind this trend is sustainability, the reduction of CO₂ emissions [1], installation of renewable sources, improvement of energy efficiency and other such measures ultimately link with the desire to have a sustainable future for the next generations. Higher education institutes, universities being the fountain house of knowledge have participated in this drive towards sustainability. Higher Education institutes (HEIs) are bulk consumers of energy and pose unique consumption patterns quite different from other

institutional buildings like hospitals, prisons, malls etc [2]. Academic schedule effects energy needs of the universities. For example, energy demand of HEIs varies considerably during summer vacations as compared to the energy consumed during regular teaching semesters. In addition, during campus timings the energy consumption stands much higher when compared to the energy consumed during off-campus timings, night and weekends [3]. Energy needs of research facilities typically located within the campus premises are on the rise. In the tropical regions the air conditioning requirement during summer season causes significantly high energy consumption as compared to winter season consumption. Newly constructed buildings in the universities have a strong dependency on air-conditioning facilities and artificial lighting especially those located in the countries of tropical region. This causes increased energy consumption and substantially high green house gases emission [4]. As per International Energy Agency (IEA) energy conserved is better than energy generated [5]. Building sector energy consumption exceeds 70% of the total energy generation in countries with hot weather conditions [6]. Energy monitoring and forecasting is the key to preserve energy consumption in the university buildings. Higher education institutes shall optimize their energy needs to obtain sustainable institutions, communities and cities. HEIs can optimize their energy demand through accurate forecasting thus reducing their adverse affects on environment.

A lot of literature on energy consumption forecasting in different sectors has been already published, for example, residential apartment buildings, homes, HEI campuses, other miscellaneous institutional buildings and at grid level as well. A number of review studies on energy consumption forecast have been also published, some of the already published works review the energy consumption forecast generally not dealing with a specific sector, some review studies are sector specific dealing with energy forecast studies in sectors like, residential [7], industrial [8] etc. Energy consumption forecast studies on HEIs have gained momentum since the past few years, some authors have focused the campus in its entirety while others have focused one or more specific building types like educational buildings, administrative blocks, student dormitories etc. Additionally some studies have focused different parameters affecting the energy consumption in HEIs. Regarding the energy forecast of HEIs sector there exists so far a single review from [9], this review dedicated to forecast studies in universities of North China was focused on energy utilization behaviors. [10] in their review on energy consumption of universities in Gulf region just touched the subject area of the current study. Heating-Ventilation & Air-Conditioning (HVAC) was determined as the largest energy consumer, whereas calendar and weather variables were identified as the main factors influencing energy consumption. Despite all the good work there are some gaps in these studies. The studies have not focused energy forecasting of universities comprehensively, none of the studies categorized the studies conducted so far on the basis of building and energy type, optimization techniques applied by different publications have not been covered in these reviews, published literature has not been segregated on the basis of forecast time horizon.

To address this review gap, this work highlights the major contributors in this field, the inputs used by authors for developed forecast models, optimizations applied etc. This study presents a productive plan for investigation. This review examines the identified literature by different angles and highlights gaps in the existing studies. It provides a ready insight to the

published literature in the area, presents the research trends and shows the room available for researchers to explore the unexplored districts of this field.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Data Collection.

Energy forecasting studies on higher education institutes have been targeted in this work. Existing work relevant to energy prediction in universities was selected through a comprehensive literature review, from conference papers and peer-reviewed journal articles. These sources offer sufficient insight to comprehend energy forecasting methods, their applications in HEIs energy systems, and function to enhance energy efficiency.

2.2. Methodological Approach

A qualitative construction was employed in this work. Sixty publications focusing on energy forecast studies on HEIs were identified. Sub-keyword system of search was adopted for identification of the relevant literature. Four levels of Sub-Keywords were employed for literature survey, Keyword combinations from these levels were used as shown in Table 1. The basic principle of counting combinations provides the total number of keyword combinations. Each sub-keyword group must combine with one keyword from each of the other groups, the total number of combinations is the product of the number of keywords in each group. This results in 150 keyword combinations; that were employed to search articles from Google Scholar database. In the advanced search feature of the Google Scholar database the option of “in the title of the article” was selected against where my words occur option, the literature search was conducted from 2014 to 2024.

Table 1. Literature Identification Methodology

Criteria	Details
Database Searched	Google Scholar
Sub-Keyword 1	'Energy'
Sub-Keyword 2	'Consumption', 'Consumed', 'Demand', 'Use', 'Usage'
Sub-Keyword 3	'Forecast', 'Forecasting', 'Predict', 'Prediction', 'Predictive'
Sub-Keyword 4	'University', 'Universities', 'Campus', 'Educational', 'Academic', 'Institutional'
Sample Keyword Combinations	'Energy consumption forecasting University', 'Energy consumption forecast University', 'Energy demand prediction Universities', 'Energy demand predictive Universities', 'Energy Usage forecasting Campus', 'Energy Usage forecast Campus', 'Energy consumption forecasting Educational', 'Energy consumption forecast Educational', 'Energy demand prediction Academic', 'Energy demand predictive Academic'
Total No. of keyword combinations	1x5x5x6=150

Table 2. Literature Identification Methodology

Criteria for selecting publication	Criteria for excluding publication
Literature published in conference papers and peer-reviewed journals	Abstracts, pre-prints, none peer-reviewed articles, book critiques and informal publications
Literature published in English	Literature in languages other than English
Publications from 2014 to 2024	Work out of the scope of the study

Using the literature identification criterion mentioned in Table 2 finally 50 publications were selected. Majority of the selected studies are journal articles, conference papers stand as second largest contributor.

3. Bibliometric Analysis of the Literature

Pertinent features of the selected articles were analyzed to present a bibliometric review of the studied papers.

3.1. Yearly Publication Trend

Fig. 1 shows the year wise publication details of the reviewed literature. The publications on the subject have steadily increased in the past representing the need of research and an interest of the researchers in this area.

Figure 1. Year wise publications record

3.2. Most Contributing Countries, Universities and Authors

Authors from different institutions across the globe have targeted the area of HEI energy forecast. Based on the first author affiliation the country wise detail against number of publications is shown in the Fig. 2.

Authors affiliated to Chinese universities have mostly contributed towards the energy forecasting studies of higher education institutes followed by the authors affiliated with the US universities as depicted by Fig. 2. This clearly marks a drive in these countries to have a clean environment and sustainable HEIs. Table 3 presents the detail of the most contributing universities based on the first author's first affiliation.

Figure 2. Country wise record of publications based on first author affiliation

Table 3. Institute Affiliation details corresponding to the First Author

First Author First Affiliation	Authors	Reference
Aksaray University, Turkey	(Hasan Yesilyurt, Yesim Dokuz, Ahmet Sakir Dokuz, 2024)	[11]
Bandung Institute of Technology, Indonesia	(Christian, Friansa, Pradipta, Haq, & Leksono, 2024)	[12]
Beijing Institute of Architectural Design, Beijing China	(Wang et al., 2024)	[13]
Chengdu Normal University, China	(Xiao Chen, Xiaobo Peng, Yanzi Li, Baiju He, 2024)	[14]
	(C. Zhang, Luo, Rezgui, & Zhao, 2024a)	[15]
	(C. Zhang, Luo, Rezgui, & Zhao, 2024b)	[16]
Dalian University of Technology, Dalian, China	(Zhao, Xu, Zhang, & Wang, 2021)	[17]
Drexel University, Philadelphia, USA	(L. Zhang, Wen, & Chen, 2017)	[18]
Fudan University, Shanghai, China	(Y. Huang, Lu, Ding, & Gu, 2015)	[19]
Hasanuddin University, Makassar, Indonesia	(Rahmah, Suyuti, & Kitta, 2023)	[20]
Incheon National University, Republic of Korea.	(Carrera & Kim, 2023)	[21]
International Institute of Information Technology-Hyderabad, India	(Lingamallu M, Garg V.2019)	[22]
Instituto Politécnico Nacional, Mexico	(Reyes et al., 2022)	[23]
Kabarak University Kenya	(Komen, Thiga, & Rugiri, 2019)	[24]
LINEACT-Lab. CESI, Arras, France	(Sadeghian Broujeny, Ben Ayed, & Matalah, 2023)	[25]
Mirpur University of Science and Technology, Pakistan	(Khuram Pervez Amber et al., 2017)	[26]
Multimedia University Malaysia	(Faiq et al., 2023)	[27]
National Institute of Posts and Telecommunications (INPT), Rabat, Morocco	(Elhabyb, Baina, Bellafkih, & Deifalla, 2024)	[28]
National Taiwan University of Science and Technology, Taipei, Taiwan	(Chou & Nguyen, 2024)	[29]
National University of Singapore, Singapore	(Deb, Eang, Yang, & Santamouris, 2016)	[30]
North China University of Technology, Beijing, China	(Han et al., 2022)	[31]
Shanghai University of Electric Power, Shanghai China	(Cao, Liu, Sun, Bavirisetti, & Xiao, 2023)	[32]
	(Ren et al., 2022)	[33]
Ss Cyril and Methodius University in Skopje, North Macedonia	(Zlatkova, Velkovski, Kokolanski, & Taskovski, 2023)	[34]

State University of Campinas, Campinas, Brazil	(Zancanaro, dos Santos, Ugarte, Giesbrecht, & de Almeida, 2019)	[35]
Thiagarajar College of Engineering, Madurai, Tamil Nādu, India	(Dharssini, Charles Raja, Karthick, & Venkatesh, 2022)	[36]
Universidad Nacional de Misiones FI-UNaM, Oberá, ARGENTINA	(Potschka, Oliveira, Mazzoletti, & Brazzola, 2022)	[37]
Universitas Sultan Ageng Tirtayasa, Serang, Indonesia	(Nurtanto, 2022)	[38]
	(R.F. Mustapa., Nordin, A.H.M., Hairuddin, M.A., Mahadan, M.E., Dahlan, N.Y., Yassin, I.M, 2024)	[39]
	(R. F. Mustapa, Mohd Nordin, W Ibrahim, Mohd Salleh, & Mahadan, 2022)	[40]
Universiti Teknologi MARA, Malaysia	(R. Mustapa, Dahlan, Yassin, & Nordin, 2020)	[41]
UAE University, UAE	(Pradeep et al, 2024)	[42]
University at Buffalo, NY, USA	(Ghassemi, Zhu, & Chowdhury, 2017)	[43]
University of Architecture and Technology, Xi'an, Shaanxi, China	(W. Cao et al., 2023)	[44]
University of Baghdad, Iraq	(Yu, Zhang, Wang, Wang, & Yang, 2024)	[45]
	(Mahdi & Hacham, 2024)	[46]
	(Jovanović, Sretenović, & Živković, 2014a)	[47]
University of Belgrade, Serbia	(Jovanović, Sretenović, & Živković, 2014b)	[48]
	(Fathi, Srinivasan, & Ries, 2019)	[49]
	(Fathi, Srinivasan, Kibert, Steiner, & Demirezen, 2020)	[50]
University of Florida, USA	(Im, Srinivasan, & Fathi, 2019)	[51]
	(Barzola-Monteses, Yanez-Pazmino, Flores-Moran, & Parrales-Bravo, 2022)	[52]
	(Adeleke & Jen, 2022)	[53]
	(P. A. Adedeji, Akinlabi, Ajayi, & Madushele, 2019)	[54]
	(P. A. Adedeji, Akinlabi, Madushele, & Olatunji, 2022)	[55]
University of Johannesburg, South Africa	(P. Adedeji, Madushele, & Akinlabi, 2018)	[56]
University of KwaZulu-Natal, South Africa	(Mlangeni, Ezugwu, & Chiroma, 2020)	[57]
University of Technology, Fuzhou, China	(L. Huang, Zou, & Gan, 2020)	[58]
University of Technology, Iraq	(Jaber, Saleh, & Ali, 2019)	[59]
University of Virginia, USA	(Heylman, Kim, & Wang, 2015)	[60]

University of Johannesburg, South Africa is the most contributing institution towards energy forecasting studies, followed by University of Florida, USA, Universiti Teknologi, Malaysia, and Dalian University of Technology, China as depicted by Table 3. It also appears that Adedeji and Mustapa are the most contributing first authors having three publications in this research area followed by Fathi, Jovanović and C. Zhang with two publications as first authors.

3.3. Publisher Details

Majority of the articles on energy forecasting studies in universities have been published by Elsevier, IEEE stands second contributing the literature on this subject as depicted by Fig. 3.

3.4. Journals and Subject Area

The selected literature was analyzed for the sources of publication, the sources includes journals, conferences. Fig. 4 represents the article wise distribution of publications in journals. Terms in the parenthesis below the journal name represents the subject area of the journal. Subject area of the journal is inherited by its publications [61]; hence it can be deduced that the articles are published in relevant field oriented journals. “Energy and

Buildings” journal of “Elsevier” is at the top with maximum number of publications in the area of HEI energy forecast. Analysis of the sources of the selected literature shows that this field has been explored in a multidisciplinary environment.

Figure 3. Publisher wise details of the reviewed literature

Energy consumption forecasting in HEIs involve technical and sociological dimensions as well, hence publications on this subject shall address both of these aspects. The reviewed articles have been published in journals covering various discipline areas. Among the selected publications the most dominating is the area of “Engineering” with an overwhelming majority of more than 75% followed by “Energy”, and “Computing” as subject areas of reviewed publications; indicating a strong tendency of technical aspects in this research area.. Further, it can be seen from Fig. 4 that only a few articles lie in the category of social sciences. It opens an opportunity window to address research gap in the field of energy consumption forecasting in universities from the perspective of social sciences.

3.5. Time Horizon Based Classification of Literature

On the basis of forecast time horizon the energy forecasting can be classified in to three broad categories; short term (STF) (when forecast horizon ranges from few minutes to a week, required for live management and control), medium term (MTF) (from few weeks to a year, used for scheduling and maintenance), and long term (LTF) (more than a year, needed for planning and expansion of the system) [62]. From the perspective of reviewed publications, short term energy forecasting has been extensively studied by the researchers with almost 66% of the reviewed articles as shown by Fig. 5. Medium term studies comprise approximately 19% of the studies.

The forecasting horizon based frequency of selected publications per year has been provided in the Fig. 6, short term studies are most popular and have attained the researchers attention from the years 2022, 2023 and 2024.

3.6. Top Ranking Publications and Authors

From the literature selected for this review a number of publications have influenced the research area as depicted by the citations received. Table 4 presents a summary of the top ranking publications relevant to the research area.

Figure 4. Journal wise distribution of the selected articles, journal subject area has been shown in the parenthesis

Figure 5. Time Horizon based Distribution of reviewed literature

Figure 6. Time horizon based yearly publications from year 2014 to 2024

Table 4. Top Ranking Papers Details

Reference	Journal/Conference (Year of Publication)	Method used	Forecast Horizon	Citations (Google Scholar)
[30]	<i>Energy and Buildings</i>	Artificial Neural Network (ANN)	Medium Term	319
[26]	(2016) <i>Energies</i>	Multiple Regression (MR)	Short Term	123
[55]	(2017) <i>International Journal of Ambient Energy</i>	Adaptive Neuro-Fuzzy Inference System (ANFIS) & ANFIS-PSO (Particle swarm optimization)	Medium Term	49
[54]	(2022) <i>Procedia Manufacturing</i>	Non-linear autoregressive neural network (NARNET) with SSA filtering	Medium Term	46
[63]	(2019) <i>Alexandria Engineering Journal</i>	LSTM	Short Term	44
[50]	(2023) <i>Sustainability</i>	Polynomial Regression, Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM).	Long Term	31
[32]	(2020) <i>Journal of Building Engineering,</i>	PSO-Stacking Improved Ensemble (PStIE) model	Short-term	26
[56]	2023 <i>IEOM Proceedings</i>	ANFIS	Short Term	23
	(2018)			

[59]	<i>International Journal on Advanced Science, Engineering and Information Technology</i> (2019)	ANN	Short Term	23
[33]	<i>Energy Reports</i> (2022)	Copula theory LSTM neural networks (Stack LSTM, Bidirectional LSTM)	Ultra-short-term Short-term	23

Authors have used data sets ranging from two weeks to several years. A larger amount of past data generally improves the forecast accuracy, while less data generally results in lower prediction accuracy as it decreases the training accuracy of the model. Chirag Deb although having only one publication in the selected articles is still the academically most influential author having 319 citations for the work published in the journal “Energy and Buildings” in 2016. The work was focused on cooling energy forecast in university buildings using artificial intelligence based techniques. Khuram occupies second position in the list with 123 citations received for the energy forecast of university buildings using statistical methods published in “Energies” journal in 2017. P.A. Adedeji occupies third position in the list having received 118 citations for three publications appearing in the selected papers.

3.7. Methods Used in Forecast Studies

Fig. 7 below represents various methods/approaches applied to forecast energy consumption at different time horizons. Different studies have also applied optimization techniques for the furtherance of prediction accuracy of the model.

Figure 7. Approaches used to develop energy forecast models

Machine Learning (ML) based forecast models being the most popular, majority of the authors applying Machine Learning models have also utilized some optimization methods to enhance prediction accuracy. Furthermore it can be seen that such models are extremely popular for short term forecasting studies. Statistical methods (SM) are popular for long term forecasts because of their capacity to identify patterns in historical data and lower computational complexity than ML methods [64]. Moreover SM performs better with limited data whereas a significantly large amount of data is required in ML methods. As majority of

the forecast work is dedicated to short term studies, Fig. 8 further details the methods applied on yearly basis.

The Machine learning models reinforced with some optimizations techniques have received authors attention in recent years for short term forecast studies as can be seen in Fig. 8.

Figure 8. Popular Short Term forecast approaches

Number of articles have tested multiple models to forecast energy, the most commonly used techniques have been shown by Table 5, LSTM being used by 44% of the studies followed by Feed Forward Neural Networks and Support Vector Regression (SVR) each comprising almost 16% of the Machine learning based short term forecast studies.

Table 5. Most used Statistical and Machine Learning algorithms for Medium term forecast

Statistical Methods	No. of Articles	Machine Learning Methods	No. of Articles
Single Linear Regression	3	LSTM	11
Multivariable Linear Regression	3	Feedforward Neural Networks	4
Autoregressive integrated moving average (ARIMA)	2	Support Vector Regression (SVR)	4
-	-	Convolutional Neural Network (CNN)	3
-	-	Multilayer perceptron (MLP)	3

Among the statistical methods almost 50% of the authors have used Single linear regression and Multivariable linear regression techniques for Short Term forecast. Table 6 presents the algorithms popular in Medium term forecast studies in universities.

Table 6. Most used Statistical and Machine Learning algorithms for Medium term forecast

Statistical Methods	No. of Articles	Machine Learning Methods	No. of Articles
Seasonal autoregressive integrated moving average (SARIMA)	2	Dense neural network	1
Multiple linear regression	2	NARNET	2
Support vector machine (SVM)	1	LSTM	1
		Multilayer Perceptron	1

It is obvious from Table 7 that the Statistical methods are preferred over other methods for LTF studies, with ARIMA and Multi linear regression being the popular techniques. Among the machine Learning methods LSTM has also been used by different authors for long term studies.

Table 7. Most used Statistical and Machine Learning algorithms for Long term forecast

Statistical Methods	No. of Articles	Machine Learning Methods	No. of Articles
ARIMA	2	LSTM	2
Multiple Linear Regression	2	CNN	1
Lasso Regression	1		
Polynomial Regression	1		

3.8. Optimization Techniques Applied in Forecasting Studies

A number of optimization techniques have been applied by different authors in energy forecast studies on HEIs to improve prediction accuracy. Table 8 presents the details of the studies applying any optimization to refine the forecast results. Since short term forecasting is the subject of most of the articles reviewed as compared to medium and long term forecast studies: the use of optimizations techniques is more common in such short term studies to enhance the prediction accuracy. Table 8 lists the optimizations applied by different models.

Table 8. Optimization techniques applied in different time horizon based forecast models

Optimization Technique	STF	MTF	LTF
Particle Swarm Optimization	5	1	-
Genetic Algorithm	1	-	-
Grid Search	1	-	-
Bayesian regularization training algorithm	2	-	-
Fuzzy C-means clustering	1	-	-
Sparrow Search Algorithm	1	-	-
Parameter tuning for ϵ and C values	1	-	-
Levenberg–Marquardt learning algorithm.	2	-	-
Hyperparameter tuning for GBR (Gradient Boosting Regressor)	1	-	-
k-means clustering	1	-	-
Dropout method to reduce overfitting	1	-	-
Automated surrogate modeling framework, COSMOS	1	-	-
improved Complete Ensemble Empirical Mode Decomposition with Adaptive Noise	1	-	-
Expectation-maximization algorithm	1	-	-
Gradient Descent	-	1	-
Jellyfish Search Optimizer	-	-	1

It is evident from Table 8 that Particle Swarm Optimization is the most commonly applied optimization technique in energy forecasting studies.

3.9. Building and Energy Type

Different authors have focused on forecasting energy for different building scenarios; some have considered aggregate energy consumption of the entire campus; others have considered a cluster of various buildings like academic buildings, libraries, administrative buildings etc, and there are studies where data from only one building from the entire campus for example residential halls etc has been used for energy forecasting. Each class of building in the campus has a specific use and subsequent energy demand and consumption pattern, academic, administrative units, laboratories for example have higher demand during campus hours, while larger amount of energy is consumed during off campus hours in the students residences. Table 9 presents the details of different time horizon forecast studies conducted on various buildings data to predict the targeted energy type. Approximately 45% of the publications reviewed have used data of a single building to forecast energy consumption. Energy forecast for a cluster of various university buildings and entire campus of the higher education institute respectively has been focused by almost equal percentage of studies. Only a few authors have focused specifically the Cooling or heating energy forecast. Majority of the publications reviewed, have worked on the aggregate energy consumption forecast (45.3%), while only electrical energy forecast has been conducted by approximately 41.5% of the studies.

Table 9. Building Type versus Energy predicted against different forecast horizon

Building Type	Percentage Studies	Energy Type	STF	MTF	LTF
Single building from the campus	45.3	Electrical	10	2	1
		HVAC	4		
		Combined	6		1
Cluster of buildings	26.4	Electrical	2	3	
		HVAC	1		
		Combined	4	1	3
Entire Campus	28.3	Electrical	3	1	
		HVAC	2		
		Combined	7	1	1

Considering the forecast studies based on the data of a single building from the higher education institute; most of the authors have used data from the academic and the departmental buildings. This is followed by the literature work using data from the student's residential halls as summarized in Table 10 for different time horizon based forecast studies.

Table 10. Forecast studies focused on a single building type

Single building Type	STF	MTF	LTF
Residential Halls	3		
Students Dining Facility	1		
Office	1		
Academic Building	7		1
Laboratory		1	
Departmental building	7	1	1
Campus Health Facility	1		

3.10. Evaluation Indices Used

Evaluation indices are used to validate the performance of prediction model. These indices are employed during validation to determine model's quality by measuring the discrepancy between predicted and actual values. Here, N is the number of observations, X_{actual} represents the actual values, and $X_{\text{predicted}}$ denotes the forecasted values. Some common indices are:

- Mean Absolute Error (MAE): This metric calculates the average of the absolute differences between predicted and actual values. It provides a straightforward measure of the error magnitude, without considering the direction of the errors. [65]

$$MAE = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N \cdot |X_{\text{actual}} - X_{\text{predicted}}|$$

where N represents the total number of data points.

- Mean Square Error (MSE): MSE calculates the average of the squared differences between predicted and actual values. It emphasizes larger errors due to the squaring process, making it useful for identifying models with substantial prediction errors. [66]

$$MSE = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N \cdot (X_{\text{actual}} - X_{\text{predicted}})^2$$

- Root Mean Square Error (RMSE): RMSE is the square root of MSE and provides a measure of the concentration of data around the line of best fit. It is commonly used in regression analysis to compare the prediction errors of different models or configurations. [66]

$$RMSE = \sqrt{MSE}$$

- Normalized Root Mean Square Error (NRMSE): NRMSE is a statistical measure used to assess the accuracy of a model, especially when comparing models with different scales. It's an extension of the Root Mean Square Error (RMSE), which quantifies the difference between predicted values and observed values. [67]

$$NRMSE = \frac{1}{X_{\max} - X_{\min}} \sqrt{\frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N \cdot (X_{\text{actual}} - X_{\text{predicted}})^2}$$

Coefficient of Variation of Root Mean Square Error (CV-RMSE): CV-RMSE is used for measuring prediction accuracy of a model relative to the variability of the data. It is useful in energy consumption forecast where scale of the data is important [67]. It is calculated by taking the Root Mean Square Error (RMSE) and normalizing it by the mean of the observed values. This allows for a scale-independent assessment of model's performance, making possible to compare models across different datasets.

$$CV_RMSE = \frac{RMSE}{\text{mean}(X_{\text{actual}})} \times 100$$

- Mean Absolute Percentage Error (MAPE): MAPE is popular to evaluate forecast accuracy. It calculates the average percentage error across all data points by comparing the absolute difference between the actual and forecasted values relative to the actual values. This percentage-based measure simplifies interpretation by providing the error in terms of the actual values' scale. [68]

$$MAPE = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N \left| \frac{X_{actual} - X_{predicted}}{X_{actual}} \right| \times 100$$

- Mean Absolute Deviation (MAD): It calculates the average absolute error between predicted and actual values, providing a straightforward measure of forecast accuracy.

$$MAD = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^N |X_{actual} - X_{predicted}|}{N}$$

- Coefficient of determination R-squared (R^2):, R^2 indicates the proportion of variance in the dependent variable that is explained by the independent variables. It is expressed as a percentage, with higher values indicating a better fit of the model to the data. [68]

$$R^2 = 1 - \frac{\sum_{i=1}^N (X_{actual} - X_{predicted})^2}{\sum_{i=1}^N (X_{actual} - X_{mean})^2}$$

Each of these indices serves a different purpose and application of any index is dependent on the analysis objectives and the data nature.

- Coefficient of Variation (CV): It is a measure of relative variability and is expressed as a percentage, with lower values indicating more stable forecasts.

$$CV = \frac{\sigma}{\mu} \times 100$$

σ (sigma) is the standard deviation of forecast errors,
 μ (mu) is the mean of forecasted values.

- Computational Time: Computational time is the time taken by a specific model to process data and provides predictions, normally in seconds. It does not show the forecast accuracy of a model. It is difficult to consider computational time as an evaluation index as it is dependent on computational resources and software, hence it is an auxiliary index parameter. [69]

Table 11 represents the summary of the error indices considered by different authors for their determining the accuracy of their forecast models.

Table 11. Summary of the Error Indices used in reviewed literature

ERROR INDICES	No of Articles
MAPE	19
RMSE	15
R2	12
MAE	9
MSE	8
CV-RMSE	5
Others	4
CV	3
R	3
MRMSE	3
MAD	3
Computational Time (sec)	3

MAPE is the most popular index in forecast studies mainly due to the precision, ease of understanding, usefulness in forecast studies. RMSE is more common in medium and long term studies as the larger errors are given more weight because of squaring. This is particularly helpful when major divergences could considerably effect the forecast results.

It has been found MAPE and RMSE are the most popular error indices in “ELECTRICAL” energy forecasting studies focused on HEIs. In the “TOTAL” or “Aggregate” energy forecasting; MAPE, RMSE and R2 are the most popular evaluation indices followed by MAE. Majority of the studies focusing on “HVAC” energy prediction have applied R2 followed by RMSE. Table 12 provides a summary of the energy type predicted in the reviewed literature along-with the evaluation indices applied.

Table 12. Literature Classification with respect to Energy Type and Error Indices used

Error Indices	HVAC	Electrical	Aggregate
CV	2	–	1
R2	4	1	7
R2	1	1	1
MSE	2	2	4
RMSE	3	5	7
CV-RMSE	–	1	4
NRMSE	–	1	2
MAE	1	2	6
MAPE	2	9	8
MAD	–	2	1
Computational Time (sec)	–	2	1

3.11. Model Inputs

Different studies have relied on a different combination of input parameters for their models to forecast energy consumption in the universities. Broadly classifying these are; meteorological conditions, institutional factors, behavioral factors, technical factors, calendar variables. These factors are discussed below:

3.11.1. Meteorological Factors

Most of the studies have used the local weather conditions as input to the forecast model (see Table 13), as energy consumption is largely dependent on meteorological conditions. Temperature, wind speed, humidity, and precipitation are the commonly used parameters. Some of the authors have also applied solar radiation as model input. In order to maintain the indoor temperatures, energy is consumed; thus energy consumption forecast is largely dependent on weather conditions.

3.11.2. Technical Factors

Building design parameters have been included in some of the studies, considering parameters such as building area, orientation and shape, equipment and lighting power density, window to wall ratio, number and area of windows. Building Age factor has also been included as input by a few authors.

Historical energy consumption data is the most common input to the forecasting model, utilized in almost all studies. Different studies have used the consumption data over a span of several years to forecast energy, while some of the studies have utilized the data of few months for their model depending on the forecast horizon. A few of the articles have considered HVAC as separate input, while remaining have used historical aggregate energy consumption as input to the forecast model.

3.11.3. Behavioral Factors

Few authors have used behavioral factor as input to their energy forecast model. Occupants energy utilization behaviors, CO₂ concentration levels to count for occupancy level, comfort level of occupants have been incorporated by certain studies. Higher education institutes typically have a large population faculty, technical and management staff, students, and guests, who have diverse energy consumption habits, hence occupants behavior may be a significant input in the forecast model. Use of occupant behavior as input by only a few of the authors in forecast studies is probably due to the unavailability of occupants behavior data. Data about the influence of consumers' on energy consumption need to be included in the forecast studies to improve accuracy of the models. Similarly the number of occupants in the campuses may be considered in forecasting models. Majority of the studies have been conducted by energy and engineering experts, there is a need to involve social sciences to collect and incorporate behavioral trends data to be applied as input to forecast models.

3.11.4. Institutional Factors

Different studies have incorporated academic schedules, data of working and holidays, summer and winter breaks as energy forecast model inputs as all these factors have significant impact on energy usage. Authors have performed energy forecast for different university buildings, some have focused teaching buildings, others have done forecast studies on administrative buildings, some studies have utilized data from the library and research laboratories; there are studies on energy forecast of dormitories as well. These buildings host diverse need and energy use intensity, therefore have a unique stamp on energy utilization. Typically data centers, research oriented buildings and labs have extensive energy consumption due to the information technology (IT) equipment, research activities and lab equipment. Buildings with large floor area have high energy consumption for example teaching buildings and libraries.

It is evident from Table 13 that energy data is being used by all the studies as input. It is found that the weather related parameters like temperature, humidity, pressure, wind etc are most commonly used inputs to the forecast models, followed by calendar information and academic schedules. There are only a few medium and long term studies: the short term studies provide a better idea of the most important inputs to be considered for forecast models. Only a few studies have used calendar information and academic schedules, however their impact on the energy demand is significant. The accuracy of the models can be improved by the inclusion of these parameters in the future studies.

Table 13. Input parameters used in forecast models

Input Parameters	No. of articles	Percentage data
Historical energy data	50	100
Meteorological factors	35	70
Calendar Information	7	14
Academic Schedule	7	14
Building Information	7	14
Occupancy Data	3	6
Occupant Behaviour	1	2
others	1	2

4. Conclusions

A comprehensive bibliometric review of the studies on energy forecasting in Higher Education Institutes; published from 2014 to 2024, has been presented. The technique helped to determine salient features of the published articles, academic trends, and influential consumption factors etc. These salient features and trends are helpful to grasp the fundamental knowledge of the field, and also specify place of origin of this knowledge. Future studies in this sector will get benefit of this detail. The analysis of reviewed publications highlights significance of universities as sustainable institutions. HEIs shall adopt sustainable practices and policies.

It was noted that Engineering and Energy are leading in this research area, although energy consumption is largely dependent on occupant's behaviors, however the role of Social Sciences and such factors as forecast model inputs is almost non-existent. Thus there is a room for social science based projects in this research area. China, USA and South Africa are the main contributors in this research area. University of Johannesburg, South Africa is the leading organizations in this research area. Adedeji and Mustapa have contributed more publications than any other author. Elsevier is the preferred publisher for this research area, and its Energy and Buildings journal has published largest percentage of the reviewed articles. Chirag Deb, Khuram Pervez and Adedeji contributed most cited articles in the field. From the reviewed articles it was noted that research laboratories and technical universities have high energy use intensity due to equipment ratings and teaching building exhibit higher energy demands due to large floor areas.

In the selected publications, energy forecasting models developed by different authors considered diverse inputs; historical energy consumption data being the most significant. Other prominent factors as model inputs included by different studies are weather conditions, user behavior, institutional influence and building related characteristics.

It was found that majority of the reviewed publications provide limited insight to the model building o excluding key information, like resolution of the data used, data division for training and testing purpose, etc.

Most of the reviewed research papers have performed forecasting for a single building of the HEI. Majority used the data from academic buildings and departmental buildings; while third popular type is the student's residential halls. Some authors used energy consumption aggregate data from the entire campus considering it as a single entity while almost same percentage of studies used data from a cluster of buildings from the campus (cumulative data from various buildings have been used).

Regarding the type of energy for which forecast models have been developed; most of the models targeted the aggregate energy forecast including electrical, heating and cooling etc while electrical energy forecast studies stood second in the overall list. However electrical energy forecast modeling is quite popular in studies focusing data from a single building. Very few authors have targeted HVAC energy consumption forecasting in short time horizon, no such study was found in medium and long time horizon.

Different modeling approaches have been highlighted to predict energy consumption. An increase in the area of energy prediction modeling in universities has been observed during the duration selected for this review work with a variety of techniques, time horizon, energy type and building types etc on a broad chronological and geographical degree. Each of the methods proposed by different authors has its own advantages for a specific application in terms of the best algorithms, and evaluation index for prediction accuracy. Most of the forecast models were developed for different data sets from different universities, with different periods and input variables. Furthermore, different error indices were used to evaluate prediction accuracy of the developed models. Repeated use of

certain algorithms in number of articles allows their interpretation as reliable and effective, for energy forecast applications. Several deep learning and machine learning methods used for energy forecasting are LSTM, Feed-Forward Neural Networks, and SVM based models. LSTM received preference over other methods, mainly for short term forecast that has comparatively complex energy consumption pattern than medium and long term studies. Machine learning methods although provide high prediction accuracy however they need a large amount of past data, difficult to model, require more computational time and powerful machines. Historical consumption, calendar and weather information are the commonly used inputs for these models. For medium and long term prediction, the use of statistical methods is more common, as variations and periodicity are less pronounced. They are less accurate and rigid when compared to ML techniques but offers easy modeling. These models sometimes also use tariff details and building information in the input pool reflecting their association long term energy consumption.

Optimizations have been commonly employed by ML based models to improve prediction accuracy, particle swarm technique is popular among such techniques.

A direct comparison between various models and algorithms proposed by different authors is possible only if a common dataset along with a specific set of evaluation indices to measure error is used in all the studies. This would certainly assist the authors to determine the best technique for a particular application.

Future of energy consumption forecasting in HEIs seems to be largely dependent on machine learning models to estimate the demand from a single building, cluster, or overall campus using dependent parameters such as historical energy demand, past meteorological data, and independent variables like calendar and occupancy information. Availability of new forecast methods, data sources like cloud computing and model-adjusted evaluation metrics, can contribute to enhance forecasting quality.

Energy forecast modeling in universities has a great prospective. It has been attempted to compile diverse practices in this research area that can be explored and enhanced further by researchers.

Some constraints of this work are: (i) Publications in English were selected; (ii) Only Google Scholar database was considered (iii) Literature published before 2014 was excluded (iii) review include papers till end of 2024, hence any addition beyond this date was not considered.

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Appendix – A

Table A1. Complete list of the reviewed literature

Reference	Country	Year	Time horizon	Energy Type	Building Type
[37]	Argentina	2022	Short Term	Electrical	Engineering Faculty building
[35]	Brazil	2019	Medium Term	Total	university campus
[15]	China	2024	Short Term	Electrical	Dormitories, laboratories, office buildings, educational buildings in a university campus
[16]	China	2024	Short Term	Total	campus buildings including dormitories, office buildings, educational buildings, libraries, and academic laboratory buildings.
[45]	China	2024	Short Term	Electrical	residential halls
[13]	China	2024	Long-Term	Total	teaching building
[32]	China	2023	Short Term	Total	campus building
[44]	China	2023	Short Term	Total	academic building
[31]	China	2022	Short Term	Electrical	campus building
[33]	China	2022	Ultra-short-Term Long-Term	Total	university campus
[17]	China	2021	Medium Term	Electrical	teaching building, student dormitory, subject research building, library building, and communication center
[58]	China	2020	Short Term	Total	college building in campus
[19]	China	2015	Short Term	Total	teaching building in the university
[25]	France	2023	Short Term	Total	office
[36]	India	2022	Short Term	Electrical	departmental building in the campus
[22]	India	2019	Short Term	HVAC	Research centre building
[12]	Indonesia	2024	Short Term	HVAC	academic building
[20]	Indonesia	2023	Short Term	Electrical	university building
[38]	Indonesia	2022	Medium Term	Electrical	departmental laboratory

[46]	Malaysia Iraq	2024	Medium Term	Total	mixed-use college building, the building contains classrooms, laboratories, and some administrative rooms, library
[59]	Iraq	2019	Short-Term	HVAC	mechanical engineering department building
[24]	Kenya	2019	Short-Term	Total	university campus
[27]	Malaysia	2023	Short Term	Electrical	main building of the university
[39]	Malaysia	2024	Short Term	Electrical	educational building
[40]	Malaysia	2022	Short Term	Electrical	educational building
[41]	Malaysia	2020	Short Term	Electrical	educational building
[23]	Mexico	2022	Medium Term	Electrical	Classroom, laboratory, library, auditorium and office buildings. workshops, Administrative buildings, campus buildings
[28]	Morocco	2024	Short to medium	Total	campus buildings
[34]	North Macedonia	2023	Short Term	Electrical	faculty building within the university
[26]	Pakistan	2017	Short Term	Total	administrative building academic building
[48]	Serbia	2014	Short Term	Heating	university campus
[47]	Serbia	2014	Short Term.	Heating	university campus
[30]	Singapore	2016	Short Term to medium Term	HVAC	1 st building Administrative building , 2 nd building offices and laboratories 3 rd building classroom, seminar halls. campus residences
[53]	South Africa	2022	Short Term	Electrical	campus residences
[55]	South Africa	2022	Medium Term	Electrical	four campus buildings at geographically different locations
[57]	South Africa	2020	Medium Term	Electrical	university buildings
[56]	South Africa	2018	Short Term.	Total	multicampus buildings
[54]	South Africa	2016	Short Term	Total	campus buildings
[21]	South Korea	2023	Short-Term	Total	17 academic buildings, including two dormitories, one sport center, and one gymnasium, educational building
[52]	Spain	2022	Short Term	Electrical	educational building
[29]	Taiwan	2024	Long-Term	Electrical	college building within university
[11]	Turkey	2024	Long Term	Total	Administrative building
[42]	UAE	2024	Medium Term	Total	Academic, dining, hostels, sports, College building
[50]	USA	2020	Long-Term	Total	Educational, Research, Residential, sports buildings
[49]	USA	2019	Long-Term	Total	educational research sports residential buildings in the campus
[51]	USA	2019	Long-Term	Electrical HVAC	university campus
[43]	USA	2017	Short-Term	Electrical	office building/laboratory facility, a library, an activity centre
[18]	USA	2017	Short-Term	Total, HVAC	health facility building in campus
[60]	USA	2015	Short-Term and Medium Term	Total	campus buildings